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**Utilization of Electronic Record Management System among Administrators
in University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital, Rivers State**

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Abstract

This study was carried out to investigate use of electronic record management system among hospital administrators in University of Port Harcourt Teaching Hospital (UPTH). The study was descriptive in design and was guided by two specific objectives and two corresponding research questions. Data were obtained from 100 administrators working in different department in the facility. The instrument used was a 15-item self-structured questionnaire on utilization of electronic record system. The test-retest method was used to ensure reliability of the instrument which was analyzed using Pearson Products Moment Correlation (PPMC) and a reliability coefficient index of 0.85 was obtained. Simple percentage was used to analyze data. Findings showed that majority (75%) of the respondents had made use of the electronic record management system which were used to some extent in the hospital. Also, majority of the respondents (65%) agreed that the electronic record system was very effective. The study recommended that awareness should be created to enlighten every administrator on the importance of electronic record management system in processing information relating to patients and security within the facility.

Keywords: utilization, electronic, record, management, administrators.